

**The Online Appendix of:
Beyond Tradition: A Hybrid Model Unveiling
News Impact on Exchange Rates**

April 8, 2024

A Appendix: Beyond Tradition: A Hybrid Model Unveiling News Impact on Exchange Rates

A.1 Attention to U.S. Dollar-Related Topics in News Articles

Figure 1: Monthly attention to U.S. Dollar-related news topics over time, measured by the average news entropies.

A.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics: Observations from 2000 to 2018

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GBP/USD	0.0000	0.0180	-0.0473	0.0483
EUR/USD	-0.0014	0.0230	-0.0619	0.0597
Stock Market News	-0.0003	0.0064	-0.0186	0.0145
Economic Development News	-0.0002	0.0112	-0.0304	0.0276
FED News	-0.0001	0.0111	-0.0247	0.0250
Micro Finance News	0.0007	0.0253	-0.0649	0.0568
International Trade News	-0.0004	0.0104	-0.0277	0.0280
CPI_US	0.0020	0.0020	-0.0035	0.0071
Money Market Rate_US	0.0001	0.0005	-0.0012	0.0016
IPI_US	0.0011	0.0047	-0.0124	0.0124
M2_US	0.0048	0.0025	-0.0015	0.0114
EPU_US	0.0127	0.5501	-1.2536	1.5021

A.3 Data Preprocessing: Addressing Nonstationarity and Outliers

Our analysis commences with an examination of the time series attributes of each variable. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test identifies nonstationarity among all variables. To address this, we apply a logarithmic transformation followed by first-order differencing to the variables. This transformation maintains monotonicity, ensuring the preservation of analytical integrity and enhancing the interpretability of impulse response analyses. Additionally, we employ the 1.5 interquartile range (IQR) method for outlier removal. As a result of this data transformation and outlier handling, all variables, including the monthly U.S. Dollar exchange rates, exhibit stationarity.

A.4 Selection of Estimation Method

We employ the Engel-Granger procedure to select the appropriate estimator for our extended Taylor model, given the I(1) characteristics of our initial time series. This involves several steps:

- 1. Residual Stationarity Test:** We conduct a cointegration regression between the exchange rate and other variables. If the residuals of this regression are stationary, indicating a cointegrating relationship, we proceed to use models such as the Vector Error Correction (VEC) model or Structural Vector Autoregression (SVAR) model with cointegration restrictions.
- 2. Model Selection:** Conversely, if the residuals are nonstationary, we construct a Vector Autoregression (VAR) model, ensuring its stability through diagnostic tests.

3. **Cointegration Assessment:** We then estimate the cointegration regression between the exchange rate and other variables, employing eigenvectors calculated via the Johansen procedure as weights.
4. **ADF Test:** Subsequently, we assess the stationarity of the residuals using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test.

Based on the nonstationarity of the residuals, the Engel-Granger procedure concludes the absence of cointegration between exchange rates and other variables, making the application of the VAR model feasible.

After selecting the VAR model using the Engel-Granger procedure, we verify the stationarity of the first differences of all logarithmized variables. Since they all exhibit stationarity, we proceed to construct the VAR model in the first differences.

A.5 Forecast Error Variance Decomposition (FEVD) Results

Table 2: FEVD for GBP/USD

Month	GBP /USD	CPI US	CPI UK	MMR US	MMR UK	IPI US	IPI UK	M2 US	M2 UK	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5	EPU US	EPU UK
1	75,4	0,1	0,1	5,5	0,1	0,0	0,4	0,5	16,2	0,1	1,2	0,1	0,1	0,0	0,0	0,3
2	60,8	0,1	0,4	7,1	1,4	0,1	0,3	7,1	14,3	0,6	1,7	0,2	1,1	2,2	0,2	2,5
3	52,1	0,2	0,4	6,0	1,7	1,9	0,3	10,7	12,1	2,8	2,1	0,1	3,9	1,9	1,3	2,4
4	47,8	1,0	0,3	7,1	2,8	2,5	0,4	10,1	11,1	2,5	2,1	0,4	3,5	2,5	3,5	2,3
5	43,1	1,1	5,4	6,5	3,7	2,7	0,5	9,4	10,1	2,4	2,4	1,1	3,5	2,3	3,5	2,5
6	41,2	1,1	5,9	6,9	3,6	3,3	0,7	9,1	9,8	2,3	3,0	1,1	3,3	2,2	4,3	2,4
7	39,2	1,3	6,0	7,0	3,5	4,9	0,7	8,8	9,4	2,5	2,8	1,3	3,2	2,7	4,2	2,6
8	37,8	1,3	5,8	6,8	3,4	4,9	0,9	9,1	10,0	2,8	3,0	1,4	3,2	2,6	4,5	2,5
9	36,6	1,6	5,7	6,5	3,5	5,0	0,9	9,2	9,7	3,1	2,9	1,4	3,2	2,9	4,9	3,1
10	35,7	1,9	5,6	6,5	3,4	4,8	1,0	9,0	9,9	3,0	2,8	1,5	3,3	3,8	4,7	3,1
11	34,9	1,9	5,6	7,1	3,3	4,7	1,0	9,4	9,7	3,1	2,8	1,5	3,3	4,1	4,6	3,0
12	34,2	1,9	5,8	7,0	3,3	4,7	1,1	9,6	9,5	3,1	3,0	1,6	3,2	4,3	4,5	3,0
13	33,5	1,9	5,7	7,2	3,5	4,6	1,1	9,5	9,7	3,2	3,0	1,6	3,3	4,2	4,9	3,2
14	33,1	2,0	5,8	7,1	3,4	4,6	1,4	9,3	9,5	3,3	3,0	1,7	3,6	4,3	4,9	3,1
15	32,8	2,3	5,8	7,1	3,4	4,7	1,4	9,2	9,4	3,2	3,0	1,7	3,7	4,3	4,8	3,1
16	32,6	2,3	5,8	7,1	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,2	9,3	3,3	3,1	1,8	3,8	4,3	4,8	3,1
17	32,5	2,3	5,8	7,2	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,2	9,3	3,3	3,0	1,9	3,7	4,2	4,8	3,1
18	32,2	2,3	5,9	7,2	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,2	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,8	4,2	4,8	3,1
19	32,1	2,3	5,9	7,2	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,2	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,8	4,2	4,8	3,1
20	32,0	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,2	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,8	4,2	4,7	3,2
21	32,0	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,6	1,5	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
22	31,9	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,5	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,8	3,2
23	31,8	2,3	5,9	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,5	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
24	31,7	2,3	5,9	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
25	31,6	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
26	31,6	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
27	31,6	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,2	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
28	31,5	2,3	6,0	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
29	31,5	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	1,9	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
30	31,4	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
31	31,4	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
32	31,4	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
33	31,4	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,6	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
34	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
35	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	3,9	4,3	4,7	3,2
36	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
37	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
38	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,4	3,4	3,3	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
39	31,3	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,3	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
40	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,3	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
41	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,1	9,3	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
42	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,3	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
43	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,3	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
44	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,4	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
45	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,4	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
46	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,4	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2
47	31,2	2,3	6,1	7,2	3,4	4,7	1,7	9,0	9,4	3,4	3,4	2,0	4,0	4,3	4,7	3,2

In [Table 2](#), column titles use the following notation: **Topic 1:** Stock Market News - *Commodities, Oil, Gas, Precious Metals, and Stock Exchange Markets*. **Topic 2:** Economic Development News - *Economic Growth, GDP, Inflation, Economic Policy, Monetary Policy, Consumption, Federal Reserves, and Unemployment*. **Topic 3:** FED News - *Central Banks, Interest Rates, Bonds, Currency Markets, Public Debt, and Government*. **Topic 4:** Microeconomic News - *Company's Profits, Sales, Financial Results, and Cash Flow*. **Topic 5:** International Trade News - *Imports, Foreign Investment, Trade in Goods and Services, and Globalization*.

Table 3: FEVD for EUR/USD

Month	EUR /USD	CPI US	CPI EU	MMR US	MMR EU	IPI US	IPI EU	M2 US	M2 EU	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5	EPU US	EPU EU
1	90,0	0,4	0,4	1,7	0,2	0,0	0,1	0,0	0,4	0,0	4,6	1,5	0,1	0,1	0,4	0,3
2	80,5	0,6	2,3	2,1	0,3	0,7	0,7	0,0	1,6	2,7	4,8	1,8	1,3	0,1	0,3	0,3
3	71,9	0,6	2,1	1,9	1,9	0,9	0,7	1,0	1,9	5,7	4,3	1,6	2,1	0,9	2,1	0,4
4	68,3	0,6	2,6	2,1	1,8	1,1	1,0	2,3	2,0	6,1	4,1	2,1	2,1	1,3	2,1	0,6
5	62,8	1,0	2,7	2,1	2,8	1,7	1,1	2,9	2,1	6,6	4,7	2,1	2,2	1,2	2,0	2,3
6	60,0	1,0	3,4	2,2	3,4	1,9	1,6	2,9	2,2	6,9	4,7	2,0	2,1	1,1	2,1	2,5
7	56,8	1,1	3,6	2,7	3,3	2,1	1,6	3,2	2,2	6,6	4,5	2,0	2,1	1,2	3,7	3,5
8	54,3	1,1	3,5	2,6	3,2	2,3	2,8	3,0	2,4	7,6	4,9	1,9	2,0	1,2	3,7	3,4
9	53,1	1,8	3,4	2,6	3,5	2,3	2,9	3,0	2,4	7,5	4,9	2,0	2,1	1,2	3,6	3,9
10	52,2	1,8	3,6	2,6	3,8	2,3	2,9	2,9	2,3	7,4	4,8	1,9	2,5	1,1	3,9	4,0
11	51,2	1,8	3,5	2,8	3,7	2,3	2,9	3,5	2,5	7,4	4,7	2,0	2,4	1,3	3,9	4,0
12	50,4	1,8	3,4	2,8	3,7	2,4	3,1	3,7	2,8	7,3	4,9	2,0	2,5	1,4	3,9	4,0
13	50,1	1,8	3,4	2,8	3,7	2,9	3,2	3,6	3,0	7,2	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,4	3,8	3,9
14	49,8	1,8	3,4	2,9	3,6	3,2	3,1	3,6	3,1	7,1	4,7	2,0	2,5	1,6	3,8	3,9
15	49,3	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,6	3,4	3,1	3,6	3,0	7,0	4,7	2,0	2,4	1,6	3,8	3,9
16	48,9	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,6	3,4	3,3	3,9	3,0	7,0	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,6	3,9	3,8
17	48,6	2,0	3,3	3,1	3,6	3,4	3,3	3,8	3,0	7,1	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,7	3,9	3,8
18	48,4	2,0	3,3	3,1	3,6	3,4	3,3	3,8	3,0	7,1	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,7	3,9	3,9
19	48,3	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,6	3,4	3,3	3,8	3,0	7,1	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,7	3,9	3,9
20	48,1	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,7	3,4	3,3	4,0	3,0	7,1	4,8	2,0	2,5	1,7	3,9	3,9
21	47,9	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,0	3,0	7,1	4,9	2,1	2,5	1,7	3,9	3,9
22	47,7	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,1	3,1	7,1	4,9	2,1	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
23	47,6	2,0	3,4	3,1	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,1	3,1	7,1	4,8	2,1	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
24	47,6	2,1	3,4	3,1	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,1	3,2	7,1	4,8	2,1	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
25	47,4	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,2	3,1	7,1	4,8	2,1	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
26	47,4	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,1	7,1	4,9	2,1	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
27	47,3	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,3	4,1	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
28	47,2	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
29	47,2	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
30	47,1	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
31	47,1	2,1	3,4	3,2	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,7	4,0	4,0
32	47,0	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,7	4,0	3,9
33	47,0	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,7	4,0	3,9
34	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,8	4,0	3,9
35	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,8	4,0	3,9
36	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,8	4,0	3,9
37	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,4	1,8	4,0	3,9
38	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
39	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,2	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
40	46,9	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
41	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
42	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
43	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
44	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
45	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
46	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9
47	46,8	2,1	3,4	3,3	3,7	3,5	3,4	4,2	3,3	7,1	4,9	2,2	2,5	1,8	4,0	3,9

In [Table 3](#), column titles use the following notation: **Topic 1:** Stock Market News. **Topic 2:** Economic Development News. **Topic 3:** FED News. **Topic 4:** Microeconomic News. **Topic 5:** International Trade News.

FEVD for EUR/USD

FEVD for GBP/USD

Figure 2:
FEVD for Foreign Exchange (FX) Rates to Summed Up Macro and News Variables

A.6 Theoretical Foundations

Literature Review on Exchange Rate Determinants This section explores the literature on exchange rate determinants as outlined by economic theory. We then compare these theoretical factors with U.S. Dollar-related topics we have identified to assess their relevance for exchange rate identification according to theory.

Stock Exchange. According to monetary models of exchange rate determination [Gavin \(1989\)](#), stock prices influence exchange rate movements through aggregate demand. Stock prices alter aggregate demand through wealth effects on consumption and the effects of capital valuation on investment decisions, and the altered aggregate demand in turn influences the floating exchange rates. Portfolio-balance models suggest an influence of the stock market on exchange rates through investors' portfolio decisions.

A number of existing studies examine the relationship of stock market and exchange rates. Some of them, [Phylaktis and Ravazzolo \(2005\)](#), [Walid et al. \(2011\)](#), [Tsai \(2012\)](#), [Xie et al. \(2020\)](#), [Coronado et al. \(2020\)](#), recognize that stock prices are helpful for predicting exchange rates.

International Trade. According to economic theory and prior research, international trade influences exchange rates through three main channels:

1) **Current Account Imbalance:** International trade may affect exchange rates through the imbalance of the current account, either in deficit or surplus. The current account encompasses net trade in goods and services, net earnings on cross-border investments, and net transfer payments. When a country runs a current account deficit, it needs to purchase foreign currency with its local currency, increasing the demand for the foreign currency relative to the local currency, thus decreasing the price of the local currency, *ceteris paribus*. [Fratzscher \(2009\)](#) found that the sizes of current accounts and US foreign investments were significant determinants of exchange rates of the USD vis-à-vis 54 foreign currencies. Recently, [Guo and Chen \(2023\)](#) concluded that international trade news events significantly influenced the RMB exchange rate. 2) **Expectations about Trade Policy Changes:** International trade influences exchange rates through expectations about changes in trade policy ([Hogan et al., 1991](#)), including alterations in international taxation (fiscal policy), globalization strategy, and actions of local government trade departments (e.g., the agency treasury in the USA). If the USA has a trade deficit, the Federal Reserve is likely to increase protectionist policies. A clear example of this is the increase in import tariffs on steel and aluminum, impacting automobile imports in the U.S. Additionally, cutting budget deficits often accompanies changes in trade policy. Currently, reducing the budget deficit is part of the U.S. plan to address the current account deficit (130.4 Billion in the first quarter of 2019). After information about the expected drop in net trade is released, there may be less available foreign currency due to a decrease in its supply on the local market (due to the expectation that the supply of foreign currency from abroad will decrease in the future and will cost more), resulting in an increase in the price of the foreign currency relative to the local currency. This devaluation of the local currency and jump in the foreign exchange rate is known as an increase in **exchange rate exposure**, potentially causing losses or gains in

the economy. 3) **Commodities Trading:** Commodities trading, as part of international trading, can influence exchange rates, especially for commodity-exporting countries. Oil, for instance, is primarily traded in U.S. dollars and may influence the USD exchange rate. Recent literature has highlighted the relationship between oil prices and the USD exchange rate. Similarly, there is a long-term relationship between precious metal prices, such as gold, and the USD exchange rate.

Central Bank. Central banks employ various tools to achieve specific economic policy goals and influence exchange rates through the financial markets channel. 1) A central bank's primary policy instrument that may affect the exchange rate is the **Monetary Policy Rate**, which is the interest rate at which commercial banks can borrow from the central bank. 2) Another tool used by central banks in the financial market is **FOREX Interventions**. The central bank buys or sells the local currency on the foreign exchange market to manipulate the exchange rate of the local currency by changing its demand. The effect of foreign market interventions, typically financed by foreign currency reserves, is significant. A notable example of currency manipulation is China's interventions on FOREX against the USD to devalue the renminbi. The only regulators of such actions are the IMF and WTO, although they have not historically been effective. 3) **Open Market Operations** is another tool employed by central banks in the financial market. When the central bank purchases or sells securities, primarily government bonds, from banks, it affects the money supply. Expansionary monetary policy involves the central bank purchasing bonds, increasing the money supply in banks, which may lead to currency devaluation in the long run, *ceteris paribus*.

Policy Rate. The relationship between exchange rates and policy rates is formalized by Taylor rule models, which are more broadly discussed below. [Rosa \(2011\)](#) tested the impact of news about policy rate decisions and central bank communications on exchange rates using intraday data of the USD exchange rate versus the Euro, British pound, Canadian dollar, Swiss franc, and Japanese yen. They analyzed a one-hour window around the announcements and found highly significant and large effects of policy rate news on exchange rates for up to one hour after the announcement.

[Clarida and Waldman \(2008\)](#) build a robust monetary exchange rate model (with inflation targeting and interest rate rule, Calvo pricing, and PPP assumptions). By employing high-frequency data (inflation announcements) for ten countries, [Clarida and Waldman \(2008\)](#) show that "bad" news for inflation is "good news" for the nominal exchange rate. Moreover, [Clarida and Waldman \(2008\)](#) argue that the sign of covariance between an inflation shock and exchange rate can show how monetary policy is conducted. They state that under inflation-targeting monetary policy exchange rate after its initial jump in response to the breaking news, should depreciate in response to inflation shock in the long run, due to the PPP assumption.

Financial Performance and Tax Revenue. In the case of a massive increase in local companies' financial performances due to a shift in productivity, the country's competitiveness might improve, and the local currency might strengthen, as the exchange rate

reflects the country’s export competitiveness. Furthermore, significant improvements in financial performance, expressed in the balance sheet, can bolster the government’s tax revenue through increased taxable income. This strengthening, in turn, fosters greater stability within the country and serves as an indicator of its competitiveness. The financial performance of the business sector also influences exchange rates through the stock market. Positive news regarding company earnings can encourage investors to purchase stocks, leading to increased demand for the local currency and a stronger exchange rate.

Exchange Rate Reserves. The size of foreign exchange (FX) reserves is identified as one of the top three determinants of post-2008 crises USD exchange rates vis-à-vis 54 countries, as noted in the ECB report [Fratzscher \(2009\)](#).

The effects outlined in this section are not accounted for in traditional macroeconomic fundamentals-based models, such as the Taylor rule model. Therefore, we anticipate capturing these effects on USD exchange rates by incorporating news into our model.

A.7 Robustness

In this section, we discuss the results of extensive robustness checks for our specification.

A.7.1 Robustness Check of U.S. Dollar-Related News Variables

We evaluate the stability and reliability of the entropy variables derived from U.S. Dollar-related news topics through a robustness test, analyzing the variability of each entropy variable over time using rolling standard deviations computed over distinct intervals (12, 24, 30, 36, 48, 60 months window sizes). By setting a threshold at 0.1, deviations beyond this threshold indicate potential instability. Variables exceeding this threshold are deemed non-robust, while those remaining within acceptable bounds are considered robust. Here we present Rolling Standard Deviation for Entropy Variables of Topics Related to the U.S. Dollar. As we see they never cross the threshold, verifying the robustness of our entropy variables.

Figure 3:
Rolling Standard Deviation for Entropy Variables of Topics Related to the U.S. Dollar

A.7.2 Model Specification Robustness

VAR models operate under the assumption that the residuals of the model follow a normal distribution. To assess the **normality of the residuals** in our VAR models, we employ the Jarque-Bera (JB) test of normality. From the JB test results presented in Table 4, it is evident that the p-values of all models exceed 0.05. This indicates that we fail to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that the residuals conform to a normal distribution.

Table 4: Jarque-Bera Test Results for Residual Normality in VAR(7) Models

Currency	Test Statistics	Critical Value	P-value	Df	Result
With News					
GBP/USD	20.77	46.19	0.937***	32	Accept H_0
EUR/USD	21.35	46.19	0.924***	32	Accept H_0
Without News					
GBP/USD	34.00	28.87	0.013**	18	Accept H_0
EUR/USD	24.29	28.87	0.146***	18	Accept H_0

Note: The Jarque-Bera test assesses the normality of residuals in the VAR(7) model. H_0 represents the null hypothesis that model residuals are normally distributed.

Serial correlation of residuals presents a potential issue in VAR models. To evaluate its presence, we conduct the Durbin-Watson test and Portmanteau Test on the residuals. The Durbin-Watson statistics, all approximately 2.0, suggest no autocorrelation in the residuals. Furthermore, the p-values of the Portmanteau test for both models—those with-

out news and those with news—are above 0.1. Therefore, we infer the absence of serial correlations between residuals.

The next issue that could arise in a VAR model is **heteroskedasticity**. To assess the presence of heteroskedasticity in our VAR model residuals, we conduct an Arch test. The p-values for both models are close to 0, indicating rejection of the null hypothesis regarding the presence of heteroskedasticity in the residuals.

Next, we assess the **stability** of our VAR models. A VAR(p)-process can be represented in a first-order vector autoregressive form, known as the companion form. Stability of the VAR(p)-process hinges on the absence of roots in or on the complex unit circle for its reverse characteristic polynomial. This condition is expressed as:

$$\det(I_K - A_1z - \dots - A_pz^p) \neq 0 \text{ for } z \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

This condition is equivalent to ensuring that all eigenvalues of the companion matrix A have a modulus less than 1. To verify this, we compute the eigenvalues of the reverse characteristic polynomial. The [Table 5](#) presents the eigenvalues obtained from the reverse characteristic polynomial of a VAR(7) model for GBP/USD and EUR/USD, representing the solutions to the characteristic equation. Each row corresponds to a specific root number, providing both the real and imaginary components of the inverse roots.

Table 5: Inverse Roots of a VAR(7) Model for GBP/USD and EUR/USD

Root Number	GBP/USD Inverse Roots	EUR/USD Inverse Roots
1	0.76, 0.00i	0.67, 0.00i
2	-0.22, 0.74i	0.52, 0.48i
3	-0.22, -0.74i	0.52, -0.48i
4	0.23, 0.40i	-0.06, 0.59i
5	0.23, -0.40i	-0.06, -0.59i
6	-0.67, 0.00i	-0.58, 0.16i
7	-0.32, 0.00i	-0.58, -0.16i

If the absolute values (moduli) of the eigenvalues of the coefficients (A matrix) in a VAR(p) process are less than one, the process is deemed stable or covariance stationary. The boxplots in [Figure 4](#), depicting the eigenvalues of our VAR(7) models, demonstrate that all eigenvalues reside within the [-1, 1] interval. This observation confirms that the moduli of the eigenvalues are less than one, validating the stability of the VAR models.

Figure 4: Eigenvalues of VAR models

To validate our model’s assumption about the **relationship between news variables and exchange rates**, we conduct multivariate F-type Granger-causality tests and Wald-type instantaneous causality tests.¹ Before conducting the tests, we ensure that all involved variables are stationary. [Table 6](#) presents the results of the multivariate Granger causality test. As shown, we cannot reject the null hypothesis of the Granger causality tests, indicating that GBP/USD and EUR/USD do not Granger-cause exogenous variables. Eventhough, as this test is conducted

The p-values of the instantaneous causality tests are below the 0.01 level of significance, leading us to reject the null hypothesis. This suggests the presence of instantaneous causality between GBP/USD and macroeconomic variables, as well as news entropies, implying that future values of news entropies and macro variables can enhance exchange rate forecasts.

The presence of instantaneous causality between exchange rates and exogenous variables, coupled wwith the absence of causal links from exchange rates to exogenous variables, aligns with the foundational assumptions of our VAR models for exchange rates and precludes the possibility of reverse causality. The identification of instantaneous causality between exchange rates and exogenous variables suggests the existence of contemporaneous relationships between these variables. This implies that fluctuations in exchange rates and exogenous variables may occur simultaneously, exerting mutual influence on each other.

¹Instantaneous Causality: x instantaneously Granger causes y if a model that uses current, past, and future values of x and current and past values of y to predict y has a smaller forecast error than a model that only uses current and past values of x and y .

Table 6: Causality Tests for Model’s Exogenous Variables and Exchange Rates

Null Hypothesis	Statistics	P-Value	Result
GBP/USD does not Granger Cause exogenous variables	F-Test = 1.2126	0.0768	Accept H_0
EUR/USD does not Granger Cause exogenous variables	F-Test = 1.1739	0.1174	Accept H_0
No instantaneous causality between GBP/USD and exogenous variables	Chi-squared = 35.582	0.002	Reject H_0
No instantaneous causality between EUR/USD and exogenous variables	Chi-squared = 34.217	0.003	Reject H_0

To determine if Granger causality tests support the hypothesis that news causes fluctuations in exchange rates, we conduct bivariate Granger causality (F-type) tests. Granger causality in this context implies that past values of news significantly affect the current exchange rate when past news values are considered as regressors. The results of these tests are provided in [Table 7](#).

Table 7: Bivariate Granger Causality Tests: Do News Granger Cause FX?

H_0 Hypothesis: News do not granger cause GBP/USD							
F-test Statistics of Bivariate Granger Causality Test							
Lag	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5	EPU_US	EPU_UK
1	6.24***	2.83*	0.00	1.58	0.09	1.21	18.58***
2	2.10	1.05	0.08	0.69	0.0	1.22	6.64***
3	2.58**	0.81	0.50	0.51	1.44	0.92	4.97***
4	1.63	0.79	0.48	2.72**	2.09*	1.41	3.92***
5	1.25	0.70	1.14	2.16*	1.57	2.73**	3.84***
6	1.11	0.66	0.94	1.77	1.31	2.483**	3.153*
7	1.16	0.80	0.92	1.61	1.23	2.16**	2.83***
H_0 Hypothesis: News do not granger cause EUR/USD							
F-test Statistics of Bivariate Granger Causality Test							
Lag	Topic 1	Topic 2	Topic 3	Topic 4	Topic 5	EPU_US	EPU_EU
1	5.07**	5.37**	0.57	5.89**	0.37	0.23	0.19
2	3.25**	3.00**	0.87	4.63***	1.56	1.10	1.45
3	2.59**	1.88	0.66	2.95**	1.37	0.68	0.89
4	1.93	1.63	0.55	2.16*	1.91	0.53	0.86
5	1.36	1.16	0.48	1.55	1.38	0.72	1.00
6	1.33	1.68	0.99	1.84*	2.19	0.48	1.19
7	1.05	1.50	1.09	1.47	1.79*	0.61	1.37**

Note: This table presents the results of Granger causality tests with the null hypothesis H_0 of no Granger causality. The significance markers denote rejection of the null hypothesis at the following levels: *** for $p < 0.01$, ** for $p < 0.05$, and * for $p < 0.1$.

The results in [Table 7](#) suggest significant predictive power for both GBP/USD and EUR/USD exchange rates by USD-related news topics and Economic Policy Uncertainty

indices. This underscores the necessity of including these variables in exchange rate models as explanatory factors. Due to the presence of correlation without causation and the risk of omitted variable bias, we incorporate even those variables that do not demonstrate Granger causality in lagged terms.

To assess whether incorporating news into our model enhances its explanatory power we **compare our model to a Taylor rule model without news**, we constructed a Taylor rule model without news and compared it with our news-augmented Taylor model for each exchange rate. Notably, the residuals of the model without news normalized after including 7 lags in the model. Residuals of the model with news had high variance, In contrast, the residuals of the models incorporating news exhibited significantly lower variances (0.0001% for GBP/USD and 0.004% for EUR/USD).

In the long term, the forecast error decomposition showed that the exchange rate itself explained 52% and 77% of the variance for GBP/USD and EUR/USD, respectively, in models without news. However, in models incorporating both macroeconomic and news variables, these values dropped to 32% and 48%. This implies that a portion of the unexplained variance in models solely reliant on macroeconomic variables (52% for GBP/USD and 77% for EUR/USD) is elucidated by the inclusion of news variables.

In summary, despite the increased complexity of models incorporating news variables, they outperformed their counterparts lacking news. This suggests that the inclusion of news variables significantly improves the models' explanatory power, warranting the assessment of additional variable coefficients.

We also **compare our model to the model with only news variables** and no macroeconomic variables. The p-value of the residuals normality test for the model with only news variables is lower (0.82 for GBP/USD and 0.21 for EUR/USD) than the corresponding p-value of the model with news and macroeconomic variables. The residuals of the model with only news variables have higher variance (0.0002 for GBP/USD and 0.0003 for EUR/USD) than the model with news and macroeconomic variables.

In the long run, the forecast error decomposition percentage explained by the exchange rate itself is 66% for GBP/USD and 69% for EUR/USD, while corresponding values lie at 32% and 48% for the models with news and macroeconomic variables, indicating that a greater percentage of exchange rate movements are explained by the endogenous variables.

Overall, our model with macroeconomic and news variables together outperforms the model with only news variables.

What is the explanatory power of the model for interest rates? We constructed an **analogous model for the U.S. money market rate**. The R^2 value of the normality test for the VAR residuals is 0.89, indicating strong explanatory power and supporting the validity of our model. The residuals exhibit a mean of $-3.3206e-18$ and a variance of $9.0227e-08$, with no detectable autocorrelation.

In summary, all of the robustness checks outlined in this section affirm the resilience of our news-enhanced exchange rate model, which integrates news into the well-established Taylor rule model. Furthermore, we demonstrate that our news-enhanced exchange rate model outperforms both the Taylor rule model without news and news-based models that do not incorporate macroeconomic variables.

B Impulse-Response Analysis

Impulse-response analysis serves as a vital tool for examining the dynamic reactions of variables to exogenous shocks. The impulse-response function (IRF) quantifies how a standard deviation shock to the i_{th} variable in y_t influences the y_{t+n} time period.

The IRF, denoted as $\phi_{ji}(n)$, is defined as:

$$\phi_{ji}(n) = e_j' A_n P e_i,$$

where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, e_i represents a selection vector, A_n is the n_{th} coefficient matrix obtained from the infinite moving average representation of y_t , and P stems from the Cholesky decomposition of the covariance matrix of y_t ($PP' = \Sigma_\varepsilon$). One notable limitation of IRF is its lack of invariance to variable ordering.

In contrast, [Koop et al. \(1996\)](#) and [Pesaran and Shin \(1998\)](#) introduced the generalized impulse-response analysis (GIRF), which is invariant to variable ordering. The GIRF, denoted as $\phi_{ji}^g(n)$, is expressed as:

$$\phi_{ji}^g(n) = e_j' \sigma_{ii}^{-1/2} A_n \Sigma_\varepsilon e_i,$$

where σ_{ii} represents the ii_{th} element of Σ_ε .

C Dynamics of Exchange Rates in Response to U.S. Dollar News

Figures 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 in this online appendix illustrate the cumulative generalized impulse-response functions of exchange rates to various news topics. Notably, the exchange rate and news series in the model are presented as the first differences of natural logarithms, facilitating clear interpretations of resulting percentage impulse responses. The reported numbers on Figures 5 to 9 represent the percentage responses of exchange rates to a 1% shock in the respective news.

[Figure 5](#) illustrates the cumulative impulse-response function (CIRF) of exchange rates concerning the first news topic - Stock Market News. It depicts the percentage response of exchange rates to a 1% shock in stock market news.² In response to a positive 1% stock market news shock, GBP/USD appreciates persistently over the full 48-month period depicted in [Figure 5](#). However, this appreciation effect is not statistically significant. Similarly, the figure reveals that the appreciation of EUR relative to USD is persistent over the entire 48-month horizon, with statistically significant appreciation observed in some periods.

²Our analysis measures the impulse-response of the monthly U.S. Dollar exchange rate's first difference to the attention given to the topic's first difference. This attention may result from positive or negative information, leading to a percentage change in the monthly U.S. Dollar exchange rate due to a one percent increase in attention to any news type. Even if the sign of this impulse-response function is not statistically significant, its fluctuations may correspond to a defined response to positive or negative news attention.

Figure 5:

Cumulative GIRFs of exchange rates to Stock Market News 1% shock.

The figure illustrates the cumulative generalized impulse response function (GIRF) of stock market (including oil commodities) news on exchange rates. The solid purple lines denote point estimates of exchange rate responses to the shock in stock market news, while the gray dotted lines represent 95% confidence bands (CB) derived from 1,000 bootstrap simulations. The gray shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval (CI). The vertical axis displays the percentage response of exchange rates to a 1% shock in stock market news. The horizontal axis corresponds to the periods after the shock, with each period representing one month).

In summary, [Figure 5](#) demonstrates the influence of the U.S. Dollar-related topic "stock market" on exchange rates. A positive shock to the attention given to the "stock market"

topic may lead to an appreciation of exchange rates vis-à-vis the USD in certain instances, resulting in a decrease in the price of the U.S. Dollar relative to foreign currencies.

Figure 6 illustrates the cumulative generalized impulse response functions of exchange rates to economic development news. It demonstrates that exchange rates do react to shocks in economic development news. From Figure 6, we observe that a positive economic development news shock has a statistically significant impact on GBP/USD in the third month and from the fifth to the ninth month.

Regarding EUR/USD, the cumulative impulse response to economic development news is statistically significant and positive from the first to the fourth month and from the sixth to the ninth month.

Figure 6: Cumulative GIRFs of exchange rates to Economic Development News 1% shock. The figure illustrates the cumulative generalized impulse response functions (GIRFs) of exchange rates to Economic Development News. The green solid lines represent point estimates of exchange rate responses to shocks in economic development news entropy, while the gray dotted lines depict the 95% confidence bands (CB) from 1,000 bootstrap simulations. The gray shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval (CI). The vertical axis displays the percentage response of exchange rates to a 1% shock in economic development news, and the horizontal axis denotes the time period after the shock (in months).

Figure 7: Cumulative GIRFs of exchange rates to FED News with a 1% shock. The figure illustrates the cumulative generalized impulse response functions (GIRFs) of exchange rates to FED news. The orange solid lines represent point estimates of exchange rate responses to a 1% shock in FED News, while the gray dotted lines depict the 95% confidence bands (CB) obtained from 1,000 bootstrap simulations. The gray shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval (CI). The vertical axis displays the percentage response of exchange rates, while the horizontal axis shows the time periods after the shock (in months).

In summary, [Figure 6](#) supports our hypothesis that economic development news influences exchange rates. Moreover, it indicates that both GBP/USD and EUR/USD appre-

ciate in response to positive economic development news shocks, with significant effects persisting for up to nine months.

On [Figure 7](#), we observe a consistent negative response of EUR/USD to FED news over the 48 months following the shock. The figure also indicates that the impact of FED news on EUR/USD is statistically significant from the first month to the fourth month after the shock. Specifically, this implies that the USD strengthens relative to the EUR in the initial quarter following increased attention to FED news in the U.S. media. Notably, the response peaks in the third month after the shock, with the EUR/USD exchange rate experiencing a 15% decline. Consequently, we infer that FED actions, as reflected in media coverage, result in a stronger U.S. Dollar compared to the Euro during the first quarter following the action, with the observed impact of a 1

All in all, [Figure 7](#) also supports the hypothesis that the U.S. Dollar related topic "FED news" influences exchange rates, as increased attention to the FED news significantly depreciates EUR/USD in the first quarter after the shock.

[Figure 8](#) illustrates the response of EUR/USD to a 1% shock in microeconomic news from US sources. It shows a decreasing trend from the second to the eighth month, followed by an increase thereafter. However, the observed responses of EUR/USD are statistically insignificant across all months.

In conclusion, the impulse response depicted in [Figure 8](#) lends support to the notion that microeconomic news influences exchange rates. Specifically, GBP/USD depreciates during the initial quarter following a microeconomic news shock.

[Figure 9](#) illustrates the response of exchange rates to a shock in international trade news. Analysis of [Figure 9](#) reveals that GBP/USD appreciates in response to heightened attention to international trade news over the entire 48-month period following the shock. Furthermore, the observed appreciation is statistically significant in certain months.

To summarize, [Figure 9](#) confirms the hypothesis that international trade news impacts exchange rates. Specifically, GBP/USD appreciates in the second quarter following the shock in international trade news.

Figure 8: Cumulative GIRFs of exchange rates in response to a 1% shock in Microeconomic News.

This figure depicts the cumulative impulse response functions (GIRFs) of exchange rates to microeconomic news, including company earnings and related information. The solid red lines represent the point estimates of exchange rate responses to a 1% shock in microeconomic news entropy, while the gray dotted lines indicate the 95% confidence bands (CB) derived from 1,000 bootstrap simulations. The gray shaded area denotes the 95% confidence interval (CI). The vertical axis displays the exchange rate response in percentage terms, while the horizontal axis indicates the time period in months after the shock.

Figure 9: Cumulative GIRFs of exchange rates in response to a 1% shock in International Trade News. This figure illustrates the cumulative generalized impulse response function (GIRF) of exchange rates to international trade news. The solid black lines represent the point estimates of exchange rate responses to a 1% shock in international trade news (entropy), while the gray dotted lines depict the 95% confidence bands (CB) derived from 1,000 bootstrap simulations. The gray shaded area indicates the 95% confidence interval (CI). The vertical axis displays the exchange rate response in percentage terms to a 1% change in the international trade news innovation, while the horizontal axis represents the time period in months after the shock.

C.1 Dynamics of Exchange Rates in Response to Selected Macroeconomic Variables

Figure 10: Cumulative GIRFs of Exchange Rates to U.S. Macroeconomic Variables

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